

The byzantine church of Prophet Ilias (Elijah), in Abysoles, Thalames, messinian Mani, Greece

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The church of Prophet Ilias (Elijah) is located close to a modern-day cemetery, in the area of Abysoles, at the village of Thalames, in the messinian province of Mani peninsula, Peloponnese, in south-western Greece. The building is modest in dimensions (5,3 x 4,5 m), constructed with large quantities of poros blocks, set in bands, partly interlaced with single lines of bricks. Rubble masonry is used for the lower parts of the church. The church belongs to a rare architectural type, identified with several terms: "single-aisle with truncated dome and external appearance of a cross-in-square- inscribed", "single-aisle barrel vaulted basilica with a dome", "cross-vaulted church with a dome", "truncated cross-in-square inscribed with arms of unequal width". The type is being acknowledged as a transitional form between the truncated cross-in-square and the traverse vault churches or just a product of experimentations of both types. The interior was originally entirely covered with murals. The largest part of the decoration has fallen off, while the remaining paintings have suffered severe damages. The conch of the apse is adorned with the figure of Prophet Elijah, and the dome of the Christ Pantocrator's bust. Other figures and scenes include the Annunciation, prelates, Life of saint Demetrios, female saints. Murals combine iconographic and stylistic features that evoke both a progressive and a conservative character and they are probably dated at the end of the 13th - early 14th century. In the church it is still performed orthodox christian ritual only at the commemoration day of Saint Ilias (Elijah) feast.

Date Range: 1250 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Thalames, Mani, Messinia, Greece

Region tags: Mani, Messinia

Thalames, a village existing from ancient era, with a continuous habitation up to present day.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: an article (see bibliography)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.efames.gr/mess_manigr.html

Notes: A cluster of similar in style and date churches in the wider area

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Other [specify]: olive grove, terraces, maquis vegetation

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Clearing

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: olive grove, terraces

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: largely, an olive grove

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: the village of Thalames

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: the village of Thalames is situated on the road leading from Messinia to the province of Laconia

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: there is a dense network of small religious places in the wider area

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: see comments for the shape of the church

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: olive grove

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: besides the olive grove and the clearings, a modern-day cemetery is built nearby the church

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

–Other [specify]: funeral (modern-day cemetery), rural (olive grove, terraces)

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: the church has not undergone evident or severe reconstruction/renovation.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: there is not evident signs of severe reconstruction

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Notes: probably the church from a female donor. The rest, cemetery and rural formations by village community or certain individuals

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: very probably; perhaps from a female donor due to the extended zone of female saints figures painted inside the church

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Orthodox Christian

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

Notes: probably there were wooden structural parts in the building but today nothing is preserved

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: brick is widely used, a typical feature of byzantine architecture.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: hewn

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: there are brick zones at the exterior walls serving decorative purposes.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: murals / fresco painting

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: murals

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Pantocrator, Virgin and other saints/holy figures

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints and Holy figures

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: People that were cured miraculously from Prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: there is a very worn-out figure of the horse that led the chariot with Prophet Ilias (Elijah) to the sky

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: painted ornamental and plant motifs (for pictures see the images in Other decoration)

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: a motif of successive square frames (for pictures see the images in Other decoration)

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: (for pictures see the images in Other decoration)

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: there are inscriptions that identify the figures and the scenes depicted

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

Notes: there are few modern-day icons inside the church of non artistic value

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: there is a specific iconographic programme depicted in the interior surfaces of the church

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: the miracles of saint Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: there is a typical byzantine iconographic programme depicted in the interior surfaces of the church, see general commentary

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: they are informative/declarative of the figures and the scenes depicted (see the image in the correspondent entry)

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

Notes: Not as a dedication of the church

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: painted geometrical and leaf ornaments

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: the general comment is that iconography combines conservative and progressive elements.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: saints and holy figures

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: the whole iconographic programme manifests a strong doctrinal character based on orthodox christian faith

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Common people who got cured by Prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: miracles of Prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes of life of Saint Dimitrios (Demetrius)

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: there is an extended zone of painted female saints, not much common in typical byzantine iconography

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: however, a modern-day cemetery is built nearby the church building

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: the church is close to a modern-day cemetery

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: It is nearby a modern-day cemetery

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: typically, by the local Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia, the Public Archaeological Service of Greek Ministry of Culture.

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The church is declared as a protected monumentes by the local Ephorate of Antiquities of Messinia, the Public Archaeological Service of Greek Ministry of Culture.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - No

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: inside the church

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: rare -commemoration day of the Prophet Elijah

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - Non-elites
 - Only locals

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 30

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: only at the feast day of Prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 10-30

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: seldom

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: only at the feast day of Prophet Ilias (Elijah)

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: modern-day funeral rituals

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sophia Germanidou , Nikos Kontogiannis undefined. The iconographic program of the Prophet Elijah church, in Thalames, Greece, 55-87.. *Byzantinische Zeitschrift*, 101(1)